

**РЕКОНСТРУКЦІЯ МОЛОЧНОЇ ЗАЛОЗИ ШЛЯХОМ
ВИКОРИСТАННЯ РОЗТЯГНУТИХ ПЕРФОРАНТНИХ
ВАСКУЛЯРИЗОВАНИХ КЛАПТІВ**

**BREAST RECONSTRUCTION BY USING STRETCHED PERFORATING
VASCULARIZED FLAPS**

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Introduction. Improving the effectiveness of treatment and the survival of patients after extensive thermal injuries, as a result, increased the number of severe scarring and contractures. One of the most common localization is the anterior surface of the body, in which in about 30% of cases irreversible changes in the breast occur. This causes functional limitations of the chest, respiratory disorders, kyphoscoliotic deformities of the spine, and distortion of the mammary glands, which is a serious aesthetic problem that leads to emotional trauma and deterioration of quality of life.

The aim of the work. To establish sources of obtaining enlarged perforating flaps from the surface of the thoracic and abdominal walls for the reconstruction of postburn scar tissues of the breast and submammary region.

Materials and methods. We conducted a number of clinical studies involving patients with lesions of the upper chest, namely the upper and lower segments of the breast and submammary fold.

The flaps were stretched using an endoexpander with an average volume of 550 ml. Surgical treatment consisted of 3 stages. In the first stage, the expander is implanted in the formed pocket. Dissection of the pocket is performed subfascial. The branches of the muscle perforants are ligated on the whole plane of the pocket, preserving the suprafascial vascular network. Dissection of the pocket cavity is performed before reaching the vascular feeding leg by 2 cm. In the second stage, the expander is expanded by introducing 0,9% NaCl in a volume of 5 to 10% of its total volume. In the third stage, the enlarged flap is formed and, after excision of scars, moves to the place of the defect.

Results On the anterior surface of the thoracic and abdominal walls it is possible to use enlarged perforating flaps based on 2, 3 anterior intercostal artery perforator (2, 3 AICAP) or thoracoacromial artery perforator (TAAP) with the inclusion of vascular networks of adjacent perforators and enlarged perforating flaps based on superior epigastric artery perforator (SEAP). From the lateral surface of the chest, flaps should be formed based on three sources - lateral thoracic artery (LTA), thoracodorsal artery (TDA), and intercostal arteries (IA). Rotation, transposition, or direct advancement methods are used to move stretched flaps from the donor areas. Each method has its advantages.

Conclusions. Stretched flaps from the anterior and lateral surface of the chest and anterior surface of the abdominal wall based on perforators of TAAP, SEAP, LTA, and TDA, with the inclusion of vascular sources adjacent to perforators, can be widely used in reconstructive practice.

Keywords: postburn deformities, breast reconstruction, perforating flaps.